

**Catalogue of Bhutan Longhorn beetles
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract. The Catalogue includes all 162 Cerambycidae species of Bhutan fauna known up to 2019 with the references to the original descriptions; 12 species were not mentioned for Bhutan in Palaearctic Cerambycidae Catalogue by Löbl & Smetana (2010); 16 species are excluded from Bhutan fauna, because those records were based on the publications for Maria Basti (West-Bengal, Darjeeling District). Bibliography of each species usually includes the geographical information from corresponding publications. Many new taxonomy positions published after 2010 are used here without special remarks.

The present work follows the previous publication on Afghanistan Cerambycidae, and is an attempt to summarize all data published up to now on Cerambycidae of Bhutan fauna.

family **CERAMBYCIDAE** Latreille, 1802

subfamily **Prioninae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Aegosomatini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Aegosoma* Audinet-Serville, 1832: 162 type species

Cerambyx scabricornis Scopoli, 1763

ornaticolle A. White, 1853: 30

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 87 - Bhutan; Danilevsky, 2012a: 113 - Bhutan;

Ren, Chen & Li, 2016: 416, 420 - Bhutan;

genus *Dinoprionus* Bates, 1875: 49 type species *Dinoprionus*

cephalotes Bates, 1875

cephalotes Bates, 1875: 50

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 87 - Bhutan.

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genus *Spinimegopis* K. Ohbayashi, 1963: 7 type species *Megopis nipponica* Matsushita, 1935

nepalensis Hayashi, 1979: 83 (*Megopis*)

Drumont & Lin, 2013: 7 - "Bhutan, Monghar Thebong, 2273 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 88 - Bhutan.

tibialis A. White, 1853: 32 (*Aegosoma*)

Komiya & Drumont, 2007: 348, 381 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 88 - Bhutan.

tribe Anacolini J. Thomson, 1857

genus *Sarmyds* Pascoe, 1867a: 410 type species *Sarmyds antennatus* Pascoe, 1867

antennatus Pascoe, 1867a: 410

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 88 - Bhutan.

tribe Macrotomini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Bandar* Lameere, 1912: 144 type species *Prinobius pascoei* Lansberge, 1884

pascoei Lansberge, 1884: 144

pascoei pascoei Lansberge, 1884: 144 [RN] (*Prinobius*)

fisheri C.O. Waterhouse, 1884: 382 (*Macrotoma*)

Quentin & Villiers, 1981: 360, 363 - Boutang; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 90 - Bhutan.

tribe Prionini Latreille, 1802

genus *Dorysthenes* Vigors, 1826: 514 type species *Prionus rostratus* Fabricius, 1793

subgenus *Lophosternus* Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 209 type species *Lophosternus buquetii* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

Cyrtosternus Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 210 type species *Lophosternus hopei* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

indicus Hope, 1831: 27 (*Prionus*)

hopei Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 210 (*Lophosternus*)

socius Gahan, 1906: 11 (*Lophosternus*)

Gahan, 1906: 10 - Bhutan; Lameere, 1911: 328 - Bhutan; Holzschuh, 1977: 337 - Bhutan; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 184 - Bhutan; Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 47 - Bhutan; Hua, 2002: 205 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 91 - Bhutan; Kumawat et al., 2015: 7882 - Bhutan.

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tribe Remphanini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Rhaphipodus* Audinet-Serville, 1832: 168 type species

Rhaphipodus suturalis Audinet-Serville, 1832

gahani Lameere, 1903: 72

Holzschuh, 1977: 337 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 95 - Bhutan.

subfamily **Lepturinae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Lepturini Latreille, 1802

genus *Corennys* Bates, 1884: 224 type species *Corennys sericata*

Bates, 1884

Pseudocorennys Pic, 1952d: 47 type species *Pyrocalymma diversicornis* Pic, 1947 (= *Pyrocalymma conspicua* Gahan, 1906

conspicua Gahan, 1906: 89 (*Pyrocalymma*)

diversicornis Pic, 1947: 17 (*Pyrocalymma*)

Holzschuh, 1977: 337 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 99 - Bhutan.

genus *Ephies* Pascoe, 1866b: 506 type species *Ephies cruentus*

Pascoe, 1866

coccineus Gahan, 1906: 87

Gahan, 1906: 87 - Bhutan; Hayashi & Villiers, 1989 - Bhutan; Hua,

2002: 207 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 100 - Bhutan.

genus *Paranaspia* Matsushita & Tamanuki, 1940: 5 type species

Leptura anaspidoidea Bates, 1873

frainii Fairmaire, 1897: 239 (*Strangalia*)

Gahan, 1906: 86 - British Bhutan; Hayashi & Villiers, 1985: 10, 70,

71 - Sikkim, NE. India : Bhutan; Hua, 2002: 223 - Bhutan; Löbl &

Smetana, 2010: 109 - Bhutan.

subfamily **Necydalinae** Latreille, 1825

genus *Ulochaetes* LeConte, 1854: 82 type species *Ulochaetes*

leoninus LeConte, 1854

vacca Holzschuh, 1982a: 65 [see: Lin & Tichý, 2014]

fulvus Pu, 1988: 303 [see: Lin & Tichý, 2014]

Holzschuh, 1982: 65 - Bhutan, Sha Gogona; Lin & Tichý, 2014: 129

- Bhutan; Wangdue Phodrang Prov.; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 142 -

Bhutan.

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subfamily **Spondylidinae** Audinet-Serville, 1832

tribe Asemini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Arhopalus* **Audinet-Serville, 1834b: 77** type species

Cerambyx rusticus Linnaeus, 1758

Criocephalus Mulsant, 1839: 63 type species *Cerambyx rusticus* Linnaeus, 1758

Criocephalum Dejean, 1835: 328 type species

Cerambyx rusticus Linnaeus, 1758 *Hylescopus* Gistel, 1856: 376 [unnecessary substitute name]

tibetanus Sharp, 1905: 159 (*Criocephalus*)

Holzschuh, 1977: 337 - Bhutan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 9 - Bhutan.

tribe Tetropiini Seidlitz, 1891

genus *Tetropium* **Kirby, 1837: 174** type species *Tetropium*

cinnamopterum Kirby, 1837

Criomorphus Mulsant, 1839: 58 [HN] type species *Callidium aulicum* Fabricius, 1775 (= *Cerambyx castaneus* Linnaeus, 1758)

confragosum Holzschuh, 1981: 93

Holzschuh, 1981: 93 - "Bhutan, Bumthang, 2600-2800 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 139 - Bhutan.

staudingeri Pic, 1901: 11

tjanshanicum Semenov, 1907: 263

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 139 - Bhutan.

subfamily **Cerambycinae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Anaglyptini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Anaglyptus* **Mulsant, 1839: 91** type species *Leptura mystica*

Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Anaglyptus* Mulsant, 1839: 91 type species *Leptura*

mystica Linnaeus, 1758

abieticola Holzschuh, 2003: 307

Holzschuh, 2003: 307 - Bhutan; Miroshnikov, Bi & Lin, 2014: 257 - West Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 143 - Bhutan.

tribe Callichromatini Swainson & Shuckard, 1840

genus *Chloridolum* **J. Thomson, 1864: 174** type species

Callichroma bivittatum A. White, 1853

subgenus *Chloridolum* J. Thomson, 1864: 174 type species

Callichroma bivittatum A. White, 1853

bivittatum A. White, 1853: 162 (*Callichroma*)

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Gahan, 1906: 198 - Bhutan; Aurivillius, 1912: 314 - Bhutan;
Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 53 - Bhutan; Bentanachs, 2012b:
47 - Bouthan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 148 - Bhutan.

genus *Polyzonus* Dejean, 1835: 324 type species *Saperda fasciata*
Fabricius, 1781

subgenus *Striatopolyzonus* Bentanachs, 2012a: 58 type species
Cerambyx tetraspilotus Hope, 1835

tetraspilotus Hope, 1835: 71 (*Cerambyx*)

latemaculatus Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 161

macropilus Gahan, 1906: 216

megaspilus Gahan, 1906: 215

microspilus Gahan, 1906: 215

quadrimaculatus A. White, 1853: 170

Bentanachs, 2012a: 58, 63, 96 - Bhutan; 2012b: 81 - Bouthan; Mitra
et al., 2017: 80 - Bhutan.

tribe Callidiini Kirby, 1837

genus *Gerdberndia* Holzschuh, 1982: 71 type species *Gerdberndia*
atricolor Holzschuh, 1982

ferrocyanea Hayashi, 1979: 87 (*Prosemanotus*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 151 - Bhutan.

tribe Callidiopini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Stenodryas* Bates, 1873: 153 type species *Stenodryas*
clavigera Bates, 1873

fascipennis Holzschuh, 1984: 347

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 158 - Bhutan.

nigromaculata Gardner, 1942: 69 (*Ceresium*)

tripunctata Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 104

Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan; Holzschuh, 1984: 347 - Bhutan;

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 158 - Bhutan; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 15 -

Bhutan.

tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802

genus *Hoplocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1864: 229 type species
Hammaticherus spinicornis Newman, 1842

spinicornis Newman, 1842a: 245 (*Hammaticherus*)

minor Pic, 1923: 8 (*Haplocerambyx*)

morosus Pascoe, 1857: 92 (*Cerambyx*)

relictus Pascoe, 1866b: 528

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Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 160 - Bhutan; Kumawat et al., 2015: 7895 - Bhutan; Majumder et al., 2015: 8244 - Bhutan.

genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891: 26 type species *Cerambyx egenus* Pascoe, 1858

subgenus *Margites* Gahan, 1891: 26 type species *Cerambyx egenus* Pascoe, 1858

decipiens Holzschuh, 1989a: 393

Holzschuh, 1989a: 393 - "West-Bhutan, Chimakothi (südlich von Thimphu), 1500 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 161 - Bhutan.

genus *Neoplocaederus* Sama, 1991: 123 [RN] type species *Plocaederus cyanipennis* J. Thomson, 1861

Plocaederus J. Thomson, 1861: 197 [HN] type species *Plocaederus cyanipennis* J. Thomson, 1861

Plocaederus Gemminger, 1872: 2799 [HN]

obesus Gahan, 1890: 51 (*Plocaederus*)

pedestris Cotes, 1889: 91 (*Plocaederus*) [HN]

Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 161 - Bhutan; Lin, 2014: 121 - Bhutan; Kumawat & et al., 2015: 7899 - Bhutan

genus *Pachydissus* Newman, 1838: 494 type species *Pachydissus sericus* Newman, 1838

schmutzenhoferi Holzschuh, 1990: 185

Holzschuh, 1990: 185 - "West-Bhutan, Paro Distr., Gedu, 2000 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 162 - Bhutan.

tribe Cleomenini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Cleomenes* J. Thomson, 1864: 161 type species *Cleomenes diamphoroides* J. Thomson, 1864

apicalis Holzschuh, 1977: 340

Holzschuh, 1977: 340 - Bhutan, 87 km von Phuntsholing; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 163 - Bhutan.

atricornis Holzschuh, 1995: 33

Holzschuh, 1995: 33 - "W-Bhutan, Thimphu Distr., Taba, 2600 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 163 - Bhutan.

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genus *Diplothorax* Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 312 type species

Diplothorax paradoxus Gressitt & Rondon, 1970

sangayi Holzschuh, 1989a: 394

Holzschuh, 1989a: 394 - "West-Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu, Taba, 2600 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 164 - Bhutan.

tribe Clytini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863: 290 type species *Callidium annulare* Fabricius, 1787

subgenus *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863b: 290 type species *Callidium annulare* Fabricius, 1787

lepesmei Pic, 1950: 507

Pic, 1950: 507 - "British Bootang" (Indes); Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 167 - Bhutan.

subgenus *Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 536 type species *Cerambyx figuratus* Scopoli, 1763

dureli Pic, 1950: 507

athatodae Chatterjee & Misra, 1971: 91

pseudofiguratus Heyrovský, 1976: 182

Pic, 1950: 507 - "British Bootang" (Indes); 1950b: 11 - British Bootang; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 166 - Bhutan.

subgenus *Immaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 536 type species *Chlorophorus kanoi* Hayashi, 1963

arciferus Chevrolat, 1863: 330 (*Amauresthes*)

pieli Pic, 1924: 15 (*Clytanthus*)

rectefasciatus Pic, 1937: 14 (*Clytanthus*)

Gahan, 1906: 263 - Bhutan; Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 220, 230 - Bhutan; Hayashi, 1979: 91 - Bhutan; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196 - Bhutan; Hua, 2002: 201 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 165 - Bhutan.

assimilis Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 165 - Bhutan.

genus *Demonax* J. Thomson, 1861: 226 type species *Demonax nigrofasciatus* J. Thomson, 1861

Elezira Pascoe, 1869: 637 type species *Clytus balyi* Pascoe, 1859

albicinctus Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)

filiformis Laporte & Gory, 1841: 95 (*Clytus*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 172 - Bhutan.

gertrudae Holzschuh, 1983: 395

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Holzschuh, 1983: 395 - Bhutan, Ungar-Lhunsi; Bhutan, 21 km O Wangdi Phodr.; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 172 - Bhutan; Danilevsky, 2013: 184 - Bhutan.

lineatus Chevrolat, 1863: 286 (*Grammographus*)

Holzschuh, 1977: 340 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana: 2010: 172 - Bhutan.

longithorax Pic, 1950: 508

Pic, 1950: 508 - British Bootang (Indes)

mariae Holzschuh, 1983: 382

Löbl & Smetana: 2010: 173 - Bhutan.

nigromaculatus Gahan, 1906: 284

Holzschuh, 1977: 340 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 173 - Bhutan.

subai Holzschuh, 1989a: 399

Holzschuh, 1989a: 399 - "West-Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu, östlich Dochu-La, Menchunang, 2400 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 173 - Bhutan.

trudae Holzschuh, 1983: 392

Holzschuh, 1983: 392 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 174 - Bhutan.

genus *Hesperoclytus* Holzschuh, 1986a: 123 type species

Hesperoclytus katarinae Holzschuh, 1986

katarinae Holzschuh, 1986a: 123

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 174 - Bhutan.

genus *Ischnodora* Chevrolat, 1863b: 332 type species *Ischnodora*

macra Chevrolat, 1863

ugyeni Holzschuh, 1989a: 397

Holzschuh, 1989a: 397 - "West-Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu, Taba, 2600 m"; "Thimphu, 2400 m"; "Distr. Haa, Haa Dzong, 2500 m"; "Bhutan, Gidaphu, 2300 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 174 - Bhutan.

genus *Perissus* Chevrolat, 1863: 262 type species *Perissus x-littera*
Chevrolat, 1863

fuliginosus Chevrolat, 1863: 328 (*Amauresthes*)

basalis Plavilstshikov, 1927: 106

Holzschuh, 1977: 340 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 175 - Bhutan.

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genus *Rhaphuma* Pascoe, 1858: 240 [RN] type species *Clytus quadricolor* Laporte & Gory, 1841

Arcyphorus Gemminger, 1872: 2938 [unjustified emendation]

Arcyphorus Chevrolat, 1863: 287 type species *Arcyphorus histrio* Chevrolat, 1863

Rhaphium A.White, 1855: 289 [HN] type species *Clytus quadricolor* Laporte & Gory, 1841

Raphuma J. Thomson, 1864: 192 [unjustified emendation]

fulgurata Gahan, 1906: 274

fulgurata bhutanica Holzschuh, 2003: 306

Holzschuh, 2003: 306 - West Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 178 - Bhutan.

manipurensis Gahan, 1906: 274

manipurensis kantiae Holzschuh, 1989a: 398

Holzschuh, 1989a: 398 - "West-Bhutan, Distr. Paro, Gedu, 2100 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 178 - Bhutan; Danilevsky, 2012a: 144 - Bhutan.

genus *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860: 456 type species *Clytus sartorii* Chevrolat, 1860

subgenus *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860: 456 type species *Clytus sartorii* Chevrolat, 1860

chhetrii Holzschuh, 1989a: 396

Holzschuh, 1989a: 396 - "West-Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu, östlich Dochu-La, Menchunang, 2400 m".

hampsoni Gahan, 1890: 54

unicarinatus Pic, 1917a: 20

Gahan, 1906: 247 - British Bhutan; Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 198 - Bhutan; Mitra et al., 2017: 82 - Bhutan.

incurvatus Chevrolat, 1863: 331

incurvatus incurvatus Chevrolat, 1863: 331 (*Amauresthes*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 182 - Bhutan; Lin, 2014: 126 - Bhutan.

incurvatus contortus Gahan, 1906: 249

biarcuatus Pic, 1917b: 6

Gahan, 1906: 249 - British Bhutan; Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 54 - Bhutan.

lepesmei Pic, 1950: 508

Pic, 1950: 508 - British Bootang (Indes); Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 182 - Bhutan.

smei Laporte & Gory, 1841: 37 (*Clytus*)

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Gahan, 1906 - 241 - Bhutan; Holzschuh, 1977: 340 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 183 - Bhutan; Majumder et al., 2015: 8245 - Bhutan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 72 - Bhutan.

stebbingi Gahan, 1906: 244

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 183 - Bhutan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 72 - Bhutan.

tribe Hesperophanini Mulsant, 1839

subtribe Hesperophanina Mulsant, 1839

genus *Stromatium* Audinet-Serville, 1834b: 80 type species

Callidium barbatum Fabricius, 1775

Solenophorus Mulsant, 1839: 65 type species *Callidium strepens* Fabricius, 1798 (= *Callidium unicolor* Olivier, 1795)

barbatum Fabricius, 1775: 189 (*Callidium*)

funestum Boisduval, 1835: 481 (*Callidium*)

tranquebaricum Gmelin, 1790: 1848 (*Callidium*)

variolosum Fabricius, 1798: 149 (*Callidium*)

Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 185 - Bhutan; Rapuzzi et al., 2019: 68 - Bhutan.

tribe Molorchini Gistel, 1848

genus *Molorchus* Fabricius, 1793: 356 type species *Necydalis umbellatarum* Schreber, 1759

subgenus *Molorchus* Fabricius, 1793: 356 type species *Necydalis umbellatarum* Schreber, 1759

Conchopterus Fairmaire, 1864: 153 type species *Necydalis umbellatarum* Schreber, 1759

Glaphyra Newman, 1840: 19 type species *Glaphyra semiusta* Newman, 1840

Laphyra Newman, 1842b: 418 [RN] type species *Glaphyra semiusta* Newman, 1840

Linomius Mulsant, 1862: 226 type species *Necydalis umbellatarum* Schreber, 1759

Sinolus Mulsant, 1862: 228 type species *Molorchus kiesenwetteri* Mulsant & Rey, 1861

densepunctatus Holzschuh, 1977: 338

Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan, Thimphu; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 189 - Bhutan.

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tribe Mythodini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Phyodexia* Pascoe, 1871: 273 type species *Phyodexia concinna* Pascoe, 1871

concinna Pascoe, 1871: 273

Gahan, 1906: 183 - Bhutan; Hua, 2002: 224 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 191 - Bhutan; Nga & Long, 2014: 29 - Bhutan.

tribe Oabriini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Chinobrium* Gressitt, 1937a: 449 type species *Chinobrium mediofasciatum* Gressitt, 1937

opacum Holzschuh, 1984c: 348 (*Stenhomalus*)

Holzschuh, 1984: 348 - SW-Bhutan; Niisato, 1998: 288 - Bhutan; 2004: 124 - Bhutan; 2005: 116, 118 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 192 - Bhutan.

genus *Obrium* Dejean, 1821: 110 type species *Cerambyx cantharinus* Linnaeus, 1767

Diozodes Haldeman, 1847: 42 type species *Callidium pallidum* Say, 1823 (= *Cerambyx maculatus* Olivier, 1795)

Phyton Newman, 1840: 19 type species *Phyton limum* Newman, 1840 (= *Cerambyx maculatus* Olivier, 1795)

posticum Gahan, 1894: 14

Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 193 - Bhutan.

tribe Oemini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Dorjia* Holzschuh, 1989a: 391 type species *Dorjia tenzingi* Holzschuh, 1989

tenzingi Holzschuh, 1989a: 392

Holzschuh, 1989a: 392 - "West-Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu, Taba, 2600 m"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 194 - Bhutan.

genus *Oemospila* Gahan, 1906a: 104 type species *Oemospila maculipennis* Gahan, 1906

Falstrostomatium Pic, 1926d: 455 type species *Falstrostomatium elongatum* Pic, 1926

maculipennis Gahan, 1906a: 105

elongata Pic, 1926d: 455 (*Falstrostomatium*)

Gahan, 1906: 105 - "Brit. Bhutan"; Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 46 - Bhutan; Hua, 2002 - 221 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 194 - Bhutan.

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genus *Oplatocera* A. White, 1853: 121 type species *Oplatocera callidioides* A. White, 1853

Hoplitocera Gemminger, 1872: 2795 [unjustified emendation]

subgenus *Epioplatocera* Gressitt, 1951: 131 type species *Oplatocera oberthuri* Gahan, 1906

oberthuri Gahan, 1906a: 108 **A: BT**

Gahan, 1906: 108 - "British Bhutan"; Hua, 2002: 221 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 194 - Bhutan.

tribe Opsimini LeConte, 1873

genus *Japonopsimus* Matsushita, 1935b: 310 [RN] type species *Paraopsimus orientalis* Matsushita, 1933

Paraopsimus Matsushita, 1933: 238 [HN] type species *Paraopsimus orientalis* Matsushita, 1933

exocentroides Holzschuh, 1984c: 342

Holzschuh, 1984: 342 - Bhutan, Chimakothe; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 195 - Bhutan.

tribe Phoracanthini Newman, 1840

genus *Nyphasia* Pascoe, 1867c: 313 type species *Nyphasia torrida* Pascoe, 1867

pascoei Lacordaire, 1868: 309

Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 195 - Bhutan.

tribe Pseudolepturini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Erythrus* A. White, 1853: 142 type species *Erythrus championi* A. White, 1853

Disidaema J. Thomson, 1860: 142 type species *Erythrus fortunei* A. White, 1853

Pseudoleptura J. Thomson, 1860: 142 [RN] type species *Erythrus championi* A. White, 1853

bicolor Westwood, 1848: 60 (*Saperda*)

Gahan, 1906: 230 - "Brit. Bhutan"; Hua, 2002: 207 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 200 - Bhutan.

tribe Compsocerini Thomson, 1864

= Rosaliini Fairmaire, 1864

genus *Rosalia* Audinet-Serville, 1834a: 561 type species *Cerambyx alpinus* Linnaeus, 1758

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subgenus *Eurybatus* J. Thomson, 1861: 233 type species *Eurybatus hariolus* J. Thomson, 1861
hariola J. Thomson, 1861: 250 (*Eurybatus*)
nakanishii Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 189
Takakuwa, 1998: 82 - Bhutan: Thimphu; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 201 - Bhutan.

tribe Stenopterini Gistel, 1848

genus *Microdebilissa* Pic, 1925b: 16 type species *Microdebilissa bipartita* Pic, 1925
Euchlanis Pascoe, 1869: 565 [HN] type species *Euchlanis collaris* Pascoe, 1869
Neodeuteromma Mitono, 1936: 32 type species *Neodeuteromma serratipenne* Mitono, 1936 (= *Microdebilissa testacea* Matsushita, 1933)
argentifera Holzschuh, 1984: 354 (*Euchlanis*)
Holzschuh, 1984: 354 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 201 - Bhutan; Danilevsky, 2013: 188 - Bhutan.

tribe Thraniini Gahan, 1906

genus *Thranis* Pascoe, 1859: 22 type species *Thranis bimaclatus* Pascoe, 1859
Singalia Lacordaire, 1872: 834 type species *Singalia spinipennis* Lacordaire, 1872 (= *Thranis gibbosus* Pascoe, 1859)
simplex Gahan, 1894: 15
simplex simplex Gahan, 1894: 15
Gahan, 1906: 237 - "British Bhutan"; Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 191 - Bhutan; Holzschuh, 1977: 340 - Bhutan; Hua, 2002: 235 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 206 - Bhutan.

tribe Tillomorphini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Epipedocera* Chevrolat, 1863: 339 type species *Epipedocera zona* Chevrolat, 1863
chakhata Gardner, 1939: 9
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 206 - Bhutan.

genus *Xystrocera* Audinet-Serville, 1834b: 69 type species *Cerambyx globosus* Olivier, 1795
globosa Olivier, 1795: 27 (*Cerambyx*)
invittata Breuning, 1957c: 1241
marginalis Goldfuss, 1805: 44 (*Callidium*)
mediovitticollis Breuning, 1957c: 1241

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diehli Heyrovský, 1967: 39
reductevittata Breuning, 1957c: 1241
vittata Fabricius, 1801: 309 (Stenocorus) [“Habitat in Brasilia” – wrong locality]
viridipicta Fairmaire, 1896: 367
Holzschuh, 1977: 338 - Bhutan.

subfamily **Lamiinae** Latreille, 1825

tribe Acanthocinini Blanchard, 1845

genus *Eoporis* Pascoe, 1864a: 15 type species *Eoporis elegans*
Pascoe, 1864

subgenus *Eoporimimus* Schwarzer, 1925b: 147 type species *Eoporis*
bifasciana Schwarzer, 1925

differens Pic, 1926e: 143

glabrosignata Pic, 1944a: 10

Hua, 2002: 207 - Bhutan.

genus *Neacanista* Gressitt, 1940: 182 type species *Neacanista*
tuberculipennis Gressitt, 1940

Hoploranomimus Breuning, 1959: 87 [= 1960e: 18] type species *Acanthocinus*
harmandi Pic, 1939 [see Huang, Liu & Gouverneur, 2015]

Paracanthocinus Breuning, 1964: 52 type species *Paracanthocinus laosensis*
Breuning, 1964 [see Huang, Liu & Gouverneur, 2015]

Sternacanista Tippmann, 1955: 128 type species *Sternacanista retrospinosa*
Tippmann, 1955

harmandi Pic, 1939: 183 (*Acanthocinus*)

Breuning, 1963a: 534 - Bhutan; Breuning, 1978: 48 - Bhutan; Löbl
& Smetana, 2010: 209 - Bhutan; Huang, Liu & Gouverneur, 2015:
557, 562 - Bhutan.

genus *Trichemeopedus* Breuning, 1975a: 357 type species
Trichemeopedus holzschuhi Breuning, 1975

holzschuhi Breuning, 1975a: 358

Breuning, 1975a: 358 - Bhutan: Thimphu; Dorjula; Löbl & Smetana,
2010: 212 - Bhutan.

genus *Trichohoplorana* Breuning, 1961b: 548 type species
Trichohoplorana dureli Breuning, 1961

juglandis Holzschuh, 1989a: 401

Holzschuh, 1989a: 401 - “West-Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu, östlich
Dochu-La, Menchunang, 2400 m”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 213 -
Bhutan.

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genus *Tuberculipochira* Breuning, 1975a: 359 type species

Tuberculipochira wittmeri Breuning, 1975

similis Breuning, 1975a: 360

Breuning, 1975a: 360 - Bhutan: Thimphu; Dorjula; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 213 - Bhutan.

wittmeri Breuning, 1975a: 359

Breuning, 1975a: 359 - Bhutan, 7 km vor Dorjula Straße Wangdi Phodrang-Thimphu; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 213 - Bhutan.

tribe Agapanthiini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Cleptometopus* J. Thomson, 1864: 95 type species

Cleptometopus terrestris J. Thomson, 1864

Acroama Jordan, 1894: 501 type species *Acroama armata* Jordan, 1894

Anapophrena Pic, 1925a: 28 type species *Anapophrena luteonotata* Pic, 1925

Apophrena Pascoe, 1866c: 323 type species *Apophrena filifera* Pascoe, 1866

Itohigea Matsushita, 1938: 102 type species *Itohigea bimaculata* Matsushita, 1938 (= *Smermus bimaculatus* Bates, 1873)

Metopoplectus Gressitt, 1936: 104 type species *Metopoplectus taiwanensis* Gressitt, 1936

Mimocleptometopus Pic, 1934c: 36 type species *Mimocleptometopus undulatus* Pic, 1934

Smermus Lacordaire, 1872: 692 type species *Smermus mniszechi* Lacordaire, 1872

aureovittatus Breuning, 1947: 63

Breuning, 1947: 63 - British-Bootan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 217 - Bhutan.

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975: 342

Breuning, 1975a: 342 - Bhutan, Gogona; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 217 - Bhutan.

pseudolivaceus Breuning, 1975a: 341

Breuning, 1975a: 341 - Bhutan, km 87 von Phuntsholing, Straße nach Thimphu; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 217 - Bhutan.

genus *Hippocephala* Aurivillius, 1920: 25 type species

Hippocephala suturalis Aurivillius, 1920

subgenus *Mimosmermus* Breuning, 1966a: 104 type species

Hippocephala fuscostriata Breuning, 1966a

fuscolineata Breuning, 1947: 64

Breuning, 1947: 64 - British-Bootan; Breuning, 1966a: 104 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 218 - Bhutan.

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genus *Pseudocalamobius* Kraatz, 1879: 116 type species
Calamobius japonicus Bates, 1873

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975a: 340

Breuning, 1975a: 340 - Bhutan: Phuntsholing, Thimphu;
Chimakothi; km 87 von Phuntsholing; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 220 -
Bhutan.

tribe Ancyronotini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Palimna* Pascoe, 1862: 346 type species *Golsinda tessellata*
Pascoe, 1857 (= *Lamia annulata* Olivier, 1797)

Apalimna Bates, 1884: 241 type species *Apalimna liturata* Bates, 1884

Cylanca J. Thomson, 1864: 58 type species *Golsinda tessellata* Pascoe, 1857 (= *Lamia annulata* Olivier, 1797)

Goniages Pascoe, 1865: 135 type species *Golsinda infausta* Pascoe, 1859

palimnoides Schwarzer, 1925a: 62 (*Apalimna*)

similis Gressitt, 1940: 131

Gressitt, 1951: 436 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 221 - Bhutan.

genus *Palimnodes* Breuning, 1938c: 330 type species *Apalimna*
ducalis Bates, 1884

ducalis Bates, 1884: 242 (*Apalimna*)

mimica Fairmaire, 1898c: 399 (*Palimna*)

Fairmaire, 1898: 399 - Boutang; Breuning, 1938a: 330 - Bhoutan;

Hua, 2002: 222 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 221 - Bhutan.

genus *Parorsidis* Breuning, 1935a: 65 type species *Parorsidis*
birmanica Breuning, 1935

Paranephelotes Breuning, 1935b: 252 type species *Paranephelotes laosensis*
Breuning, 1935

nigrosarsa Pic, 1926a: 15 (*Ostedes*)

nigrosarsa nigrosarsa Pic, 1926a: 15 (*Ostedes*)

birmanica Breuning, 1935a: 65

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 221 - Bhutan.

tribe Apodasyini Lacordaire, 1872

genus *Mimovitalisia* Breuning, 1959: 82 type species *Zodale*
tuberculata Pic, 1924

wittmeri Breuning, 1975a: 354

Breuning, 1975a: 354 - Bhutan, Nobding, 41 km O Wangdi,
Phodrang; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 224 - Bhutan.

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genus *Paroricopis* Breuning, 1958a: 35 type species *Paroricopis latefasciata* Breuning, 1958

latefasciata Breuning, 1958a: 36

Breuning, 1958a: 36 - Bootan, Lintsé; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 225 - Bhutan.

genus *Pseudectatosia* Breuning, 1940: 209 type species *Pseudectatosia strandiella* Breuning, 1940

strandiella Breuning, 1940: 209

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 225 - Bhutan.

genus *Rhodopina* Gressitt, 1951: 439 [RN] type species *Rhodopis pubera* J. Thomson, 1857

Rhodopis J. Thomson, 1857b: 174 [HN] type species *Rhodopis pubera* J. Thomson, 1857

parassamensis Breuning, 1975a: 352

Breuning, 1975a: 352 - Bhutan, Nobding, 41 km O Wangdi, Phodrang; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 226 - Bhutan.

genus *Spinozorilispe* Breuning, 1963b: 83 type species *Spinozorilispe fusca* Breuning, 1963b

fusca Breuning, 1963b: 84

Breuning, 1963b: 84 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 227 - Bhutan.

genus *Zotalemimon* Pic, 1925a: 29 type species *Zotalemimon apicale* Pic, 1925 (= *Sybra posticata* Gahan, 1894)

Diboma J. Thomson, 1864: 46 [HN] type species *Diboma tranquilla* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Hathlia procera* Pascoe, 1859)

Donyisia Gressitt, 1940: 179 type species *Sydonia costata* Matsushita, 1933

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975a: 350 (*Diboma*)

bhutanum Breuning, 1975b: 38 (*Diboma*) [see Danilevsky, 2014: 221-222]

Breuning, 1975a: 350 - Bhutan, Phuntsholing; Breuning, 1975b: 34, 38 - Bhutan, Phuntsholing; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 228 - Bhutan.

tribe Apomecynini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Apomecyna* Dejean, 1821: 108 type species type species *Saperda alboguttata* Megerle, 1802 (= *Lamia histrio* Fabricius, 1793)

Anapomecyna Pic, 1925a: 29 type species *Anapomecyna luteomaculata* Pic, 1925

Crassapomecyna Breuning, 1958e: 492 type species *Apomecyna crassiuscula*

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Fairmaire, 1896

Mecynapus J. Thomson, 1858: 187 type species *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856

Pseudoalbana Pic, 1895: 77 type species *Pseudoalbana lameerei* Pic, 1895

Vocula Lacordaire, 1872: 587 type species *Vocula irrorata* Lacordaire, 1872 (= *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856)

leucosticta Hope, 1831: 28 (*Callidium*)

lineata Pic, 1937: 14

luteomaculata Pic, 1925a: 29 (*Anapomecyna*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 228 - Bhutan.

genus *Ropica* Pascoe, 1858: 247 type species *Ropica piperata* Pascoe, 1858

dorsalis Schwarzer, 1925b: 145

burketi Gressitt, 1937b: 609

langana Pic, 1945: 3

rufescens Pic, 1926b: 5

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 234 - Bhutan.

tribe Astathini Thomson, 1864

genus *Plaxomicrus* J. Thomson, 1857d: 57 type species *Plaxomicrus ellipticus* J. Thomson, 1857

latus Gahan, 1901: 70

Gahan, 1901: 70 - Bhutan; Breuning, 1956a: 424, 463 - Inde: British Bootang; Breuning, 1966b: 662 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 237 - Bhutan.

tribe Batocerini J. Thomson, 1864

genus *Apriona* Chevrolat, 1852: 414 type species *Lamia germari* Hope, 1831

subgenus *Apriona* Chevrolat, 1852: 414 type species *Lamia germari* Hope, 1831

Anapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species: *Apriona submaculosa* Pic, 1917

Cylindrapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species *Monochamus cylindricus* J. Thomson, 1857

Humeroapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species *Lamia swainsoni* Hope, 1840

Mesapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species *Apriona punctatissima* Kaup, 1866

Parapriona Breuning, 1948a: 17 type species: *Parapriona brunneomarginata* Breuning, 1948

germari Hope, 1831: 28

germari germari Hope, 1831: 28 (*Lamia*)

cribrata J. Thomson, 1878: 57

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deyrollei Kaup, 1866: 7

Jiroux, 2011: 59 - Bouthan; Kumawat et al., 2015: 7888 - Bhutan.

genus *Batocera* Dejean, 1835: 341 type species *Cerambyx rubus*

Linnaeus, 1758

Megacriodes Pascoe, 1866c: 259, 271 type species *Megacriodes saundersii* Pascoe, 1866

Semibatocera Kriesche, 1915: 115 type species *Batocera calana* Parry, 1844 (= *Batocera parryi* Hope, 1845)

Tyrannolamia Kriesche, 1915: 115 type species *Batocera wallacei* Thomson, 1858

horsfieldi Hope, 1839: 42 A: BT

adelpha J. Thomson, 1859: 77

kuntzeni Kriesche, 1915: 139

Gilmour & Dibb, 1948: 88 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 237 - Bhutan; Kumawat et al., 2015: 7887 - Bhutan.

roylei Hope, 1833: 64 (*Lamia*) A: BT

coreana Kolbe, 1886: 238

downesii Hope, 1845b: 76

ebenina Vollenhoven, 1871: 211

orientalis Kriesche, 1915: 119

porus Parry, 1844: 454 [= 1845: 86] (*Lamia*)

princeps L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 551

Gilmour & Dibb, 1948: 10 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 237 - Bhutan; Mitra et al., 2017: 84 - Bhutan.

tribe Ceroplesini J. Thomson, 1860

subtribe Crossotina J. Thomson, 1864

genus *Paramoechotypa* Breuning, 1938d: 230 type species

Paramoechotypa fasciculata Breuning, 1938

fasciculata Breuning, 1938b: 230

Breuning, 1938b: 230 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 241 - Bhutan.

tribe Dorcaschematini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Olenecamptus* Chevrolat, 1835: 134 type species

Olenecamptus serratus Chevrolat, 1835 (= *Saperda biloba* Fabricius, 1801)

Authades J. Thomson, 1857b: 191 type species *Authades indianus* J. Thomson, 1857

Ibidimorphum Motschulsky 1860: 152 type species *Ibidimorphum octopustulatum* Motschulsky, 1860

biloba Fabricius, 1801: 324 (*Saperda*)

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bilobus quinquemaculatus L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1948: 234
Saha et al., 2013: 3 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 264 - Bhutan.

tribe Exocentrini Pascoe, 1864

genus *Exocentrus* Dejean, 1835: 339 type species *Cerambyx balteatus* Fabricius *sensu* Dejean, 1835 (= *Cerambyx lusitanus* Linnaeus, 1767)

Bicolorihirtus Kusama & Tahira, 1978: 9 type species *Exocentrus venatoides* Kusama & Tahira, 1978

Formosexocentrus Breuning, 1958c: 322 type species *Exocentrus variepennis* Schwarzer, 1925

alboguttatus Fisher, 1925: 240

alboguttatus obscurior Pic, 1929: 30

rufescens Pic, 1929: 30

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 309 - Bhutan; Danilevsky, 2012b: 733 - Bhutan.

championi Fisher, 1940: 207

kashmirensis Breuning, 1957a: 277

Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 412, 418 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 310 - Bhutan.

collarti Breuning, 1958b: 41

Breuning, 1958b: 41 - "Bhutan"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 310 - Bhutan.

diversiceps Pic, 1931: 259

lateralis Pic, 1936: 299 [HN]

lateraloides Breuning, 1958c: 300

rufoamplius Breuning, 1958c: 300

rufobasipennis Breuning, 1958c: 300

testaceus Fisher, 1932: 322

Breuning, 1958: 300 - Bhutan : Marià Basti; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 310 - Bhutan.

explanatidens Pic, 1930a: 58

Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 413, 417 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 310 - Bhutan.

parassamensis Breuning, 1975a: 355

Breuning, 1975a: 355 - Bhutan, Phuntsholing; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 311 - Bhutan.

subniger Breuning, 1975a: 356

Breuning, 1975: 356 - Bhutan, Chimakothi; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 311 - Bhutan.

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tribe Gnomini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Imantocera* Dejean, 1835: 341 type species *Lamia plumosa*
Olivier, 1797

Himantocera Gistel, 1848: xi [unjustified emendation]

Himantocera Pascoe, 1866: 288 [unjustified emendation]

penicillata Hope, 1831: 28 (*Lamia*)

Kumawat et al., 2015: 7891 - Bhutan.

tribe Mesosini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Cacia* Newman, 1842c: 290 type species *Cacia spinigera*
Newman, 1842

subgenus *Ipocregyes* Pascoe, 1864a: 96 type species *Ipocregyes*
newmani Pascoe, 1866

Falsoereis Pic, 1925b: 25 type species *Falsoereis cephalotes* Pic, 1925

basialboantennalis Breuning, 1958b: 6

Breuning, 1958b: 6 - "Bhutan"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 269 -
Bhutan.

bootanana Breuning, 1968a: 693

Breuning, 1968a: 693 - Bootan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 269 -
Bhutan.

cephalotes Pic, 1925b: 25 (*Falsoereis*)

Breuning, 1939:452 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 269 -
Bhutan.

subgenus *Falsomesosella* Pic, 1925b: 27 type species
Falsomesosella minor Pic, 1925

Gyarancita Breuning, 1963c: 9 type species *Gyarancita rondoni* Breuning, 1963

bhutanensis Breuning, 1968b: 859 (*Mesosella*)

Breuning, 1968b: 859 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 271 -
Bhutan.

genus *Mesocacia* Heller, 1926: 32 type species *Mesocacia*
assamensis Heller, 1926 (= *Ereis multimaculata* Pic, 1925)

multimaculata Pic, 1925b: 24 (*Ereis*)

assamensis Heller, 1926: 33

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 271 - Bhutan.

genus *Mesosa* Latreille, 1829: 124 type species *Cerambyx*
curculionoides Linnaeus, 1760

subgenus *Aplocnemia* Stephens, 1831: 236 type species *Cerambyx*

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nubilus Gmelin, 1790 (= *Lamia nebulosa* Fabricius, 1781)

Aphelocnemia Stephens, 1832: 414 [emendation, not in usage]

Haplocnemia Agassiz, 1846b: 172 [unjustified emendation]

Helixoea Pascoe, 1865: 124 type species *Agelasta rupta* Pascoe, 1862

affinis Breuning, 1936: 306

affinis affinis Breuning, 1936: 306

Breuning, 1936: 306 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 271 - Bhutan.

tribe Monochamini Gistel, 1848

genus *Acalolepta* Pascoe, 1858: 247 type species *Acalolepta pusio*
Pascoe, 1858

Cypriola J. Thomson, 1864: 16 type species *Cypriola acanthocinoides*
J. Thomson, 1864

Dihammus J. Thomson, 1864: 80 type species *Monochamus longicornis*

J. Thomson, 1857 (= *Monochamus australis* Boisduval, 1835)

Haplohammus Bates, 1884: 239 type species *Monohammus luxuriosus* Bates, 1873

Neanthes Pascoe, 1878: 372 type species *Monohammus curialis* Pascoe, 1858 (= *Monochamus subluscus* J. Thomson, 1857)

Niphohammus Matsushita, 1932: 170 type species *Niphohammus korolensis*
Matsushita, 1932

griseipennis J. Thomson, 1857: 296 (*Monochamus*)

Breuning, 1944: 472 - Bhoutan; Rondon & Breuning, 1970: 464, 466
- Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 275 - Bhutan; Saha et al., 2013: 4
- Bhutan.

sikkimensis Breuning, 1935c: 250 (*Dihammus*)

sikkimensis nigrina Breuning, 1975a: 344

Breuning, 1975a: 344 - "Bhutan: km 87 von Phuntsholing;
Phuntsholing-Timphu"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 276 - Bhutan.

sikkimensis rufoantennata Breuning, 1975a: 345

Breuning, 1975a: 345 - Bhutan, Changra 18 km S Tongsa; Löbl &
Smetana, 2010: 276 - Bhutan.

wittmeri Breuning, 1975a: 343

Breuning, 1975: 343 - Bhutan: 21 km O Wangdi Phodrang; Changra
18 km S Tongsa; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 276 - Bhutan.

genus *Anoplophora* Hope, 1839: 43 type species *Anoplophora*
stanleyana Hope, 1839

Callophophora J. Thomson, 1864: 76 [unnecessary replacement name]

Cyriocrates J. Thomson, 1868: 181 type species *Oplophora horsfieldii* Hope, 1842

Falsocyriocrates Pic, 1953: 2 type species *Cyriocrates elegans* Gahan, 1888

Melanauster J. Thomson, 1868: 181 type species *Cerambyx chinensis* Forster,
1771

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- Micromelanauster* Pic, 1931d: 49 type species *Monochamus bowringii*
A. White, 1858
Mimonemophas Breuning, 1961c: 309
Oplophora Hope, 1839: 42 type species *Oplophora sollii* Hope, 1839
stanleyana Hope, 1839: 43
angustata Pic, 1934a: 11 [HN]
chapaensis Breuning, 1950a: 511
gloriosa Tippmann, 1953: 152
grisea Tippmann, 1953: 153
melancholica Tippmann, 1953: 153
tonkinea Breuning, 1943c: 285 [RN]
Breuning, 1944: 284 - Bhoutan; Breuning, 1961a: 337 - Boutan;
Lingafelter & Hoebeke, 2002: 137 - Bhutan; Hua, 2002: 194 -
Bhutan; N. Ohbayashi, Ogawa & Su, 2009: 314 - Bhutan; Löbl &
Smetana, 2010: 278 - Bhutan.

- genus *Blepephaeus* Pascoe, 1866a: 249** type species *Monohammus succintor* Chevrolat, 1852
Parablepephaeus Breuning, 1980c: 171 type species *Parablepephaeus lumawigi*
Breuning, 1980
Perihammus Aurivillius, 1925: 21 type species *Perihammus bifasciatus*
Aurivillius, 1924 (= *Monohammus infelix* Pascoe, 1856)
ocellatus Gahan, 1888c: 262 (*Monochamus*)
pauloperforatus Pic, 1930b: 17 (*Epepeotes*)
wittmeri Breuning, 1975a: 342 (*Cypriepepeotes*)
Breuning, 1975a: 342 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 279 -
Bhutan.

- genus *Epepeotes* Pascoe, 1866d: 249** type species *Lamia lusca*
Fabricius, 1787
Diochares Pascoe, 1866c: 303 type species *Cerambyx fimbriatus* Olivier, 1797
(=*Lamia fimbriata* Olivier, 1795 = *Cerambyx desertus* Linnaeus, 1758)
Falsomonochammus Pic, 1943: 3 type species *Falsomonochammus*
diverseglabratus Pic, 1943
Mengelotes L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1941: 43 type species *Mengelotes*
ambiguus L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1941
uncinatus Gahan, 1888a: 271
lineatus Pic, 1944b: 14 (*Pseudopsacothea*)
salvazai Pic, 1925a: 18
Breuning, 1943: 148, 224 - Bhoutan britannique; Breuning, 1961a:
325 - Boutan; Hua, 2002: 207 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 280
- Bhutan; Kumawat et al., 2015: 7891 - Bhutan; Mitra et al., 2017:
86 - Bhutan.

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genus *Monochamus* Dejean, 1821: 106 type species *Cerambyx sutor* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Monochamus* Dejean, 1821: 106 type species *Cerambyx sutor* Linnaeus, 1758

Ceratades Gistel, 1834: 29 [unnecessary substitute name]

Meges Pascoe, 1866c: 272 type species *Monohammus gravidus* Pascoe, 1858

Monohammus Dejean, 1835: 340 [unjustified emendation]

bootangensis Breuning, 1947: 9

Breuning, 1947: 8 - British Bootang; Breuning, 1961a: 366 - Boutan;

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 282 - Bhutan.

hiekei Breuning, 1964: 445

Breuning, 1964: 445 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 282 - Bhutan.

subconvexicollis Breuning, 1967a: 183

Breuning, 1967a: 183 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 283 -

Bhutan.

genus *Paraleprodera* Breuning, 1935b: 253 type species *Lamia crucifera* Fabricius, 1793

stephana A. White, 1858: 406 (*Monohammus*)

fasciata W.-K. Wang, 1997: 440

officinatrix A. White, 1858: 409 (*Monohammus*)

quadrinotata J. Thomson, 1865a: 554 (*Archidice*)

Breuning, 1943: 154, 268 - Bhoutan; Breuning, 1961a:334 - Boutan;

Hua, 2002: 222 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 284 - Bhutan.

genus *Paraepepeotes* Pic, 1935: 16 type species *Paraepepeotes breuningi* Pic, 1935

Parepepeotes Breuning, 1938b: 182 [unjustified emendation]

albomaculatus Gahan, 1888a: 272 (*Epepeotes*)

Breuning, 1943: 147, 215 - Bhoutan britannique; Breuning, 1961a:

324 - Boutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 284 - Bhutan; Danilevsky,

2011: 322 - Bhutan "North India".

genus *Peribasis* J. Thomson, 1864: 86 type species *Monohammus helenor* Newman, 1851

pubicollis Pascoe, 1866c: 231

albisparsa Ritsema, 1888: 203

Breuning, 1944: 338 - Bhoutan; Breuning, 1961a: 346 - Boutan;

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 285 - Bhutan.

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genus *Pseudomeges* Breuning, 1944: 299 type species
Hammaticherus marmoratus Westwood, 1848
marmoratus Westwood, 1848: 11 (*Hammaticherus*)
Rondon & Breuning, 1970: 443 - Boutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010:
286 - Bhutan.

tribe Morimopsini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Aconodes* Pascoe, 1857: 106 type species *Aconodes montanus*
Pascoe, 1857
Centrura Guérin-Méneville, 1843: 61 [HN] type species *Centrura costata*
Guérin-Méneville, 1843
Dioxippe J. Thomson, 1861: 355 type species *Centrura divaricata* Coquerel, 1852
Chambaganorum Pic, 1925a: 27 type species *Chambaganorum angustatum* Pic, 1925
breuningi Gouverneur, 2015: 88
submontanus Breuning, 1975a: 345 [HM]
Breuning, 1975a: 345 - Bhutan, 21 km O Wangdi Phodrang; Löbl &
Smetana, 2010: 288 - Bhutan; Gouverneur, 2015: 88 - Bhoutan.
lima Holzschuh, 1989b: 173
Holzschuh, 1989b: 173 - Bhutan, Distr. Thimphu; Löbl & Smetana,
2010: 288 - Bhutan.
multituberculatus Breuning, 1947: 6 (*Centrura*)
Breuning, 1947: 6 - “Inde britannique: British Bootang”; Breuning,
1961a: 310 - Boutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 288 - Bhutan.
piniphilus Holzschuh, 2003: 309
Holzschuh, 2003: 309 - Bhoutan, West Bhutan (Thimphu Province),
Motihang (bei Thimphu); Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 288 - Bhutan.

genus *Morimopsis* J. Thomson, 1857b: 182 type species
Morimopsis lacrymans J. Thomson, 1857
glabripennis Holzschuh, 2003b: 308
Holzschuh, 2003: 308 - Bhutan, Ungar-Lhunsi; Löbl & Smetana,
2010: 288 - Bhutan.
unicolor Breuning, 1975a: 347
Breuning, 1975a: 347 - Bhutan: Pele La; Gogona; Löbl & Smetana,
2010: 288 - Bhutan.

tribe Phytoeciini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Linda* J. Thomson, 1864: 122 type species *Amphionycha*
femorata Chevrolat, 1852
subgenus *Linda* J. Thomson, 1864: 122 type species *Amphionycha*

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femorata Chevrolat, 1852

Miocris Fairmaire, 1902a: 245 type species *Miocris nigroscutata* Fairmaire, 1902

rubescens Hope, 1831: 28 (*Saperda*)

rubescens rubescens Hope, 1831: 28 (*Saperda*)

bisbimaculata Pic, 1930a: 59 (*Miocris*)

fulva Fairmaire, 1895: 188

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 293 - Bhutan; Mitra et al., 2017: 86 - Bhutan.

genus *Nupserha* Chevrolat, 1858: 358 [RN] type species *Saperda*

fricator Dalman, 1817, designated by Desmarest, 1860: 326

Sphenura Dejean 1835:350 [HN - preoccupied by Lichtenstein, 1820 for Aves]
type species *Saperda fricator* Dalman, 1817, designated by Desmarest, 1860: 326

annulata J. Thomson, 1857c: 147 (*Stibara*)

annulata annulata J. Thomson, 1857c: 147 (*Stibara*)

subannulicornis Pic, 1916: 7 (*Oberea*)

Breuning, 1960c: 36 - "Bootan"; Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 139 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 295 - Bhutan.

flavipennis Breuning, 1950b: 16

Breuning, 1960c: 32 - "Bootan"; Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 142 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 295 - Bhutan.

pallidipennis L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 552 (*Phytoecia*)

pallidipennis pallidipennis L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 552 (*Phytoecia*)

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 295 - Bhutan.

rotundicollis Breuning, 1950c: 263

Breuning, 1960c: 49 - "Bootan"; Breuning, 1967b: 786 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 295 - Bhutan.

spinifera Gressitt, 1948: 63

spinifera spinifera Gressitt, 1948: 63

Breuning, 1960c: 28 - "Bootan"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 296 - Bhutan.

genus *Oberea* Dejean, 1835: 351 type species *Cerambyx linearis*

Linnaeus, 1760

subgenus *Oberea* Dejean, 1835 351 type species *Cerambyx linearis*

Linnaeus, 1760

Isosceles Newman, 1842d: 318 type species *Isosceles macilenta* Newman, 1842

consentanea Pascoe, 1867b: 426

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imbrevicollis Pic, 1928: 16

posticata Pic, 1926b: 10 [HN]

rufopyga Pic, 1926b: 10

unicolor Breuning, 1956b: 236

Breuning, 1962: 161 - Boutan; Hua, 2002: 219 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 296 - Bhutan.

genus *Obereopsis* Chevrolat, 1855: 289 type species *Obereopsis obscuritarsis* Chevrolat, 1855

Paroberea Kolbe, 1893: 79 type species *Paroberea fuscipes* Kolbe, 1893 (= *Obereopsis obscuritarsis* Chevrolat, 1855)

annulicornis Breuning, 1957b: 107

Breuning, 1957b: 108 - Bootan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 300 - Bhutan.

aterrima Breuning, 1949: 17

Breuning, 1957b: 73 - Bootan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 300 - Bhutan.

flavodiscalis Breuning, 1982: 29

flavodiscalis bhutanensis Breuning, 1975a: 362

Breuning, 1975a: 362 - Bhutan: Tongsa; Phuntsholing-Timphu; Changra; Löbl & Smetan, 2010: 300 - Bhutan.

sericeoides Holzschuh, 2006: 488

Holzschuh, 2006: 488 - Bhutan : Changra, 18 km S Tonga; km 87 von Phuntsholing; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 301 - Bhutan.

tribe Pteropliini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Egesina* Pascoe, 1864a: 49 type species *Egesina rigida* Pascoe, 1864

subgenus *Egesina* Pascoe, 1864a: 49 type species *Egesina rigida* Pascoe, 1864

Gyaritodes Breuning, 1947: 38 type species *Gyaritodes inspinosus* Breuning, 1947 [see: Holzschuh, 2017: 141]

Neoegesina Fisher, 1925: 215 type species *Neoegesina ornata* Fisher, 1925

Platyzeargyra Fisher, 1925: 213 type species *Platyzeargyra bakeri* Fisher, 1925

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975a: 338 (*Similosodus*)

Breuning, 1975a: 338 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 314 - Bhutan.

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genus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842e: 370 [NP] type species *Mesosa bigibbera* Newman, 1842

subgenus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842e: 370 [NP] type species *Mesosa bigibbera* Newman, 1842

Acroptycha Quedenfeldt, 1888: 209 type species *Acroptycha spinifera* Quedenfeldt, 1888

Alyattes J. Thomson, 1864: 48 type species *Alyattes guineensis* J. Thomson, 1864

Cormia Pascoe, 1864b: 281 type species *Cormia ingrata* Pascoe, 1864

Eurycotyle Blessig, 1873: 210 type species *Eurycotyle maacki* Blessig, 1873

Incamelomorpha Pic, 1926b: 4 type species *Pterolophia depensis* Pic, 1926

Paralophia Aurivillius, 1925: 30 [HN] type species *Paralophia quadrinodosa* Aurivillius, 1925

Praonetha Dejean, 1835: 344 [NO] type species *Lamia crassipes* Wiedemann, 1823

Praonetha Pascoe, 1862: 348 [HN, RN] type species *Prioneta albosignata* Blanchard, 1853

Prioneta Blanchard, 1853: 292 [RN] type species *Prioneta albosignata* Blanchard, 1853

Prionetopsis J. Thomson, 1864: 49 type species *Prionetopsis balteata* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Lamia inaequalis* Fabricius, 1801)

Theticus J. Thomson, 1858: 190 type species *Theticus biarcuatus* J. Thomson, 1858

***bottangensis* Breuning, 1968b: 854**

Breuning, 1968b: 854 - Bhutan: Paedong; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 319 - Bhutan.

***consularis* Pascoe, 1866a: 240 (*Praonetha*)**

cervina Gressitt, 1939: 74

crisulata Fairmaire, 1896b: 391 (*Praonetha*)

notaticeps Pic, 1934b: 12

ochreomaculipennis Breuning, 1968b: 852

Breuning, 1968b: 852 - Bhutan.

***densefasciculata* Breuning, 1938b: 269**

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 320 - Bhutan.

***sthenioides* Breuning, 1938b: 309**

***sthenioides grossepunctipennis* Breuning, 1969b: 660**

Breuning, 1969b: 660 - Bouthan: Pedong, Distr. Darjeeling; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 321 - Bhutan.

***wittmeri* Breuning, 1975a: 337**

Breuning, 1975a: 337 - Bhutan, Chimakothi; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 321 - Bhutan.

subgenus *Sociopraonetha* Breuning, 1961b: 542 type species *Pterolophia nigrocincta* Gahan, 1894

***nigrocincta* Gahan, 1894: 69**

atrofasciata Pic, 1925c: 138 (*Stesilea*)

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socia Gahan, 1894: 70

Breuning, 1965: 457 - "Bhutan"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 321 - Bhutan.

genus *Similosodus* McKeown, 1945: 292 [RN] type species *Sodus verticalis* Pascoe, 1865

subgenus *Similosodus* McKeown, 1945: 292 [RN] type species *Sodus verticalis* Pascoe, 1865

Sodus Pascoe, 1864a: 96 [HN] type species *Sodus verticalis* Pascoe, 1865

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975d: 338

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 322 - Bhutan.

genus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840: 466 type species *Lamia grisator* Fabricius, 1787

subgenus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840: 466 type species *Lamia grisator* Fabricius, 1787

Anomamomus Fehraeus, 1872: 194 [RN] type species *Sthenias leucaspis* Fehraeus, 1872 (= *Lamia leucaspis* Fabricius, 1801)

Chalarus Fehraeus, 1873: 45 [HN] type species *Sthenias leucaspis* Fehraeus, 1873 (= *Lamia leucaspis* Fabricius, 1801)

Thysanodes Newman, 1842d: 292 type species *Thysanodes jucunda* Newman, 1842

pseudodorsalis Breuning, 1938b: 369

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 322 - Bhutan.

tribe Saperdini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Callundine* J. Thomson, 1879: lvi type species *Callundine lacordairei* J. Thomson, 1879

Pseudosaperda Pic, 1903: 121 type species *Pseudosaperda goliath* Pic, 1903

lacordairei J. Thomson, 1879: lvii

goliath Pic, 1903: 121 (*Pseudosaperda*)

Hua, 2002: 199 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 322 - Bhutan.

genus *Glenea* Newman, 1842d: 301 type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831

subgenus *Glenea* Newman, 1842d: 301 type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831 *Accola* Jordan, 1894: 503 [HN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)

Accolona E. Strand, 1942: 392 [RN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)

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- Cryllis* Pascoe, 1867b: 363 type species *Cryllis clytoides* Pascoe, 1867
Hapochoron Gistel, 1848: x [RN]
Sphenura Dejean, 1835: 350 [HN] type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831
- capriciosa* J. Thomson, 1857c: 142
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 324 - Bhutan.
- crucifera* Gahan, 1889: 222
Gahan, 1889: 222 - Bhotan (N. India); Breuning, 1966b: 685 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 325 - Bhutan.
- flava* Jordan, 1895: 270
atroapicalis Pic, 1926c: 21
binhensis Breuning, 1956d: 683
Breuning, 1966b: 685 - Bhoutan; Rondon & Breuning, 1970: 528, 534 Bhutan.
- indiana* J. Thomson, 1857c: 141 (*Stibara*)
Breuning, 1956c: 173 - Bootan; 1966b: 683 - Bhoutan; Rondon & Breuning, 1970: 528, 533 - Bootan; Hua, 2002: 210 - Bhutan; Lin et al., 2009: 158, 173 - “Central Bhutan, Gaylegphug Prov. [26°52'N 90°30'E], Gaylegphug, alt. 250 m”; “Bhoutan, Andlais”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 325 - Bhutan; Saha et al., 2013: 6 - Bhutan.
- lecta* Gahan, 1889: 219
Breuning, 1966b: 682 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 325 - Bhutan.
- plagiata* Gardner, 1930: 164
Gardner, 1930: 163 - Bhutan; Breuning, 1956d: 691 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 326 - Bhutan.
- quaduordecimmaculata* Hope, 1831: 28 (*Saperda*)
argus J. Thomson, 1857c: 145
Breuning, 1956d: 684 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 326 - Bhutan.
- sanctaemariae* J. Thomson, 1857c: 141 (*Stibara*)
Breuning, 1966b: 686 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 326 - Bhutan.
- virens* Aurivillius, 1925: 19
virens virens Aurivillius, 1925: 19
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 327 - Bhutan.
- zalinensis* Gahan, 1897: 478
Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 327 - Bhutan.

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genus *Glenida* Gahan, 1888b: 65 type species *Glenida suffusa*
Gahan, 1888

cyaneipennis Gahan, 1888b: 66

cyaneipennis cyaneipennis Gahan, 1888b: 66

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 327 - Bhutan.

genus *Malloderma* Lacordaire, 1872: 842 type species *Malloderma*
pascoei Lacordaire, 1872

pascoei Lacordaire, 1872: 842

tonkineum Pic, 1932: 151

Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 327 - Bhutan.

genus *Ossonis* Breuning, 1954: 429, 432 type species *Ossonis*
clytomima Pascoe, 1856

indica Breuning, 1954: 429, 432

Breuning, 1954: 429, 432 - Bhutan: Bootan.

genus *Serixia* Pascoe, 1856: 45 type species *Serixia apicalis* Pascoe,
1856

subgenus *Serixia* Pascoe, 1856: 45 type species *Serixia apicalis*
Pascoe, 1856

Iole Pascoe, 1858: 254 [HN] type species *Iole prolata* Pascoe, 1858

Iolea Pascoe, 1862a: 353 [RN]

bootangana Breuning, 1958d: 213

Breuning, 1958d: 213 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 331 -
Bhutan.

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Supplement

Several records for “Bhutan” by Löbl & Smetana (2010) (partly repeated the records by Breuning, 1960a, 1961a, 1961d, 1966b, 1967b) were evidently based on records for Maria Basti [27°08'N, 88°39'E - Inde: West-Bengal, Darjeeling District] by Breuning (1940, 1947, 1948a, 1948b, 1953, 1956a, 1956c, 1956d, 1957b, 1958, 1960b, 1961b, 1963d, 1965), Villiers (1958) and so were not connected with the territory of moderb Bhutan, but with the distrixt of Darjeeling (Inde: West-Bengal).

The list of such names is shown bellow.

family **DISTENIIDAE** J. Thomson, 1861

subfamily **Disteniinae** J. Thomson, 1861

tribe Disteniini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Distenia* Lepeletier & Audinet-Serville, 1828: 485 type

species *Distenia columbina* Lepeletier & Audinet-Serville, 1828

Apheles Blessig, 1872: 165 type species *Apheles gracilis* Blessig, 1872

Basisvallis Santos-Silva & Hovore, 2007:23 type species: *Distenia agroides* Bates, 1870

Sakuntala Lameere, 1890: ccxiii type species *Sakuntala kalidasae* Lameere, 1890

Thelxiope J. Thomson, 1864: 226 [HN] type species *Thelxiope viridicyanea* J. Thomson, 1864

Thomsonistenia Santos-Silva & Hovore, 2007:3 [RN] type species: *Thelxiope viridicyanea* J. Thomson, 1864

subgenus *Distenia* Lepeletier & Audinet-Serville, 1828: 485 type

species *Distenia columbina* Lepeletier & Audinet-Serville, 1828

pici Villiers, 1958: 264

Villiers 1958: 264 - “Maria Basti, Bouthan” [Inde: West-Bengal, Darjeeling District, Maria Basti, 27°08'N, 88°39'E]; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 85 - Bhutan.

subfamily **Lamiinae** Latreille, 1825

tribe Acanthocinini Blanchard, 1845

genus *Rondibilis* J. Thomson, 1857a: 306 type species *Rondibilis*

bispinosa J. Thomson, 1857

subgenus *Rondibilis* J. Thomson, 1857a: 306 type species *Rondibilis*

bispinosa J. Thomson, 1857

Eryssamena Bates, 1884: 251 type species *Eryssamena saperdina* Bates, 1884

Parenes Aurivillius, 1928: 23 type species *Parenes lineata* Aurivillius, 1928

Polimeta Pascoe, 1864a: 13 type species *Ostedes spinosula* Pascoe, 1860

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bastiana Breuning, 1961b: 545

Breuning, 1961b: 545 - "Boutan: Maria Basti"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 211 - Bhutan.

tribe Apomecynini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Estigmenida* Gahan, 1894: 82 type species *Estigmenida variabilis* Gahan, 1894

albolineata Breuning, 1940: 211

Breuning, 1940: 211 - Britisch Bootan: Maria Basti; Breuning, 1960a: 137 - Bootan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 231 - Bhutan.

tribe Astathini Thomson, 1864

genus *Lasiophrys* Gahan, 1901: 71 type species *Lasiophrys latifrons* Gahan, 1901

latifrons Gahan, 1901: 72

Breuning, 1956a: 424, 471 - Bootan: Maria Basti; Breuning, 1966b: 662 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 237 - Bhutan.

tribe Monochamini Gistel, 1848

genus *Pseudomacrochenus* Breuning, 1943: 271 type species *Pelargoderus antennatus* Gahan, 1894

affinis Breuning, 1960b: 30

Breuning, 1960b: 30 - Boutan: Maria Basti; Breuning, 1961a: 335 - Boutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 286 - Bhutan.

tribe Morimopsini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Morimopsidius* Breuning, 1948a: 4 type species *Morimopsidius triangularis* Breuning, 1948

triangularis Breuning, 1948a: 5

hiekei Breuning, 1964: 445 (*Monochamus*)

Breuning, 1948a: 5 - "Maria Basti, Bhoutan britannique"; 1961a: 318 - Boutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 288 - Bhutan.

tribe Phytoeciini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Obereopsis* Chevrolat, 1855: 289 type species *Obereopsis obscuritarsis* Chevrolat, 1855

Paroberea Kolbe, 1893: 79 type species *Paroberea fuscipes* Kolbe, 1893 (= *Obereopsis obscuritarsis* Chevrolat, 1855)

bimaculicollis Breuning, 1949: 20

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bipuncticollis bootanana Breuning, 1957b: 89

Breuning, 1957b: 89 - Bootan: Maria Basti; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 300 - Bhutan.

sericea Gahan, 1894: 96 (*Oberea*)

Breuning, 1957b: 71 - Bootan: Maria Basti; Breuning, 1967b: 803 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 301 - Bhutan.

truncata Breuning, 1957b: 109

Breuning, 1957b: 109 - Bootan: Maria Basti; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 301 - Bhutan.

tribe Pteropliini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Paramesosella* Breuning, 1940: 143 type species

Paramesosella fasciculata Breuning, 1940

alboplagiata Breuning, 1948b: 3

Breuning, 1948b: 3 - "Brit. Bootan: Maria Basti"; Breuning, 1963d: 190 - "Bhutan: Maria Basti"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 316 - Bhutan.

genus *Paramispilopsis* Breuning, 1947: 36 type species

Paramispilopsis indica Breuning, 1947

indica Breuning, 1947: 37

Breuning, 1947: 37 - British-Bootany: Maria Basti; 1961d: 282 - Boutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 316 - Bhutan.

genus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842e: 370 [NP] type species *Mesosa bigibbera* Newman, 1842

subgenus *Hylobrotus* Lacordaire, 1872: 538 type species *Hylobrotus ploemi* Lacordaire, 1872

obscuroides Breuning, 1938b: 274

Breuning, 1961d: 252 - Boutan; 1965: 368 - "Bhutan: Maria Basti"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 318 - Bhutan.

subgenus *Mimoron* Pic, 1925a: 27 type species *Mimoron phungi* Pic, 1934

ropicoides Breuning, 1968b: 857

Breuning, 1968b: 857 - Bhoutan: Maria Basti; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 318 - Bhutan.

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tribe Saperdini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Glenea* Newman, 1842d: 301 type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831.

subgenus *Glenea* Newman, 1842d: 301 type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831.

Accola Jordan, 1894: 503 [HN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)

Accolona E. Strand, 1942: 392 [RN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)

Cryllis Pascoe, 1867b: 363 type species *Cryllis clytoides* Pascoe, 1867

Hapochoron Gistel, 1848: x [RN]

Sphenura Dejean, 1835: 350 [HN] type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831

didymoides Breuning, 1956c: 166

Breuning, 1956c: 166 - Boutan: Maria Basti; Breuning, 1966b:682 - Bhoutan; Lin et al., 2009: 175 - Bhutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 325 - Bhutan.

ornata Gahan, 1889: 223

Breuning, 1956d: 677 - Bhutan: Maria Basti; 1966b: 685 - Bhoutan; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 326 - Bhutan.

pseudoluctuosa Breuning, 1953: 22

Breuning, 1953: 22 - Bootan: Maria Basti; 1956d: 777 - Bhutan: Maria Basti; Cools, 1993: 108 - "British Bootang: Maria Basti"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 326 - Bhutan.

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